

DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT POWER SUPPLY IN THE DIRECTION OF ENERGY EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article describes the foundations for determining the didactic principles of teaching the subject “Electricity supply in agriculture and water management”, and also scientifically studied the principles of teaching, taking into account the specifics of the subject.

Key words: didactic principles, pedagogical foundations, educational processes, didactics, agriculture, water management, educational subject.

The general principles of didactics are used in the training of advanced specialists in higher educational institutions. The didactic principles of the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management serve as social requirements for the organizational and pedagogical foundations of educational processes and the norms to be observed in its management.

In our opinion, the principles of the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management are based on the following:

- 1) Ways to implement the goals and tasks arising from the needs and demands of the society before the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management;
- 2) Laws of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management;
- 3) Didactic-methodical conditions of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management in educational institutions.

According to the authors of the “Didactics” textbook, “Principles are general didactic categories. They are general rules that apply to all components of educational processes of all types, levels, and subjects of education” [1].

Therefore, the principles affect the purpose and tasks of the science, the laws of teaching, the didactic-methodical conditions of the teaching of the

sciences based on the needs and demands of the society. In addition, the qualities of the general didactic category are the rules related to the types, levels, subjects, components of the educational process. It should be noted that the above-mentioned is a near-necessity in teaching the methodology of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management. At the same time, it concludes that all those who teach this subject in higher education should know these principles.

The main problems of didactics are the following: to reveal the laws of the educational process, determining the content of the education, the most effective teaching methods and organization.

Each subject, including the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management, requires specific characteristics, specific methods, and organizational forms of teaching.

In recent years, special attention has been paid not only to education and upbringing of students, but also to their development. For this reason, it is necessary to include the professional development of students in the process of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management. The task of the methodology of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management is to find answers to three questions: why to teach, what to teach and how to teach (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The answer to the first question involves the formulation of learning objectives. It is known that higher education institutions fulfill the social order.

This means that the objectives of the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management are determined by the needs of society. The development of society leads to changes in educational goals. Its content directly depends on educational goals. For example, if the goal is to form a scientific worldview in students, in that case, the content of the science of electricity

supply in agriculture and water management should include material of an ideological nature. If the goal is to form students' opinions about the main directions of scientific and technical development, then relevant material should be included in this lesson.

Thus, teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management in the higher education system has its own characteristics requires consideration not only in terms of goals and objectives, but also based on teaching principles.

So what is the principle? What is the essence of the principle? What are the principles of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management?

We understand the principles of teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management in higher education as the organization and implementation of the teaching processes of these subjects. At the same time, we understand the initial conditions, general rules and requirements that determine the selection of educational content, forms, and methods.

The principles embody the requirements that the teacher and the learner must follow during the teaching process. These issues determine the pedagogically correct selection of the form, guidelines, and tools of the activities used based on the content of the selected educational topic, and ensure the success of education. After all, the principles of the teaching subject of methodology envisage and establish activities aimed at the formation of scientific-practical worldview, spiritual-morality, meaningful and reasonable needs.

1. The scientific principle. Teaching the science of electricity supply in agriculture and water management is based on scientific principles. Any information can contribute to development only if it has a scientific basis. After all, scientific knowledge is tested in this experiment, provides the development of science and technology, and represents the compatibility of civilization with progress. It is known that the scientific principle of teaching is implemented in the section "educational subject". The subject of study is viewed on the basis of the information provided by science. In this case, scientific knowledge leads to assimilation of existing laws and understanding of theoretical information. Because every subject taught in educational institutions, including the subject of electricity supply in agriculture and water management, consists of the general foundations of the relevant science. In this case, the number of concepts and categories in the science, the richness of the content, the breadth of the scope of

application are higher than the educational subject. The educational subject was created based on the age characteristics, real learning opportunities, and interests of the learners. Therefore, it can be said that the information in the educational subjects is also based on scientific principles. According to the scientific principle, in the process of acquiring scientific knowledge, the fundamentals of science, intellectual abilities and creative thinking are developed. At the same time, the scientific outlook is gaining content. The principle of scientific character requires that the studied educational material corresponds to the modern achievements of electrical engineering science. In addition, this objective requires that it does not contradict scientific facts, theories, and laws. Adherence to the scientific principle in the teaching of electrical engineering means that the information conveyed to the student must be based on evidence. This can be achieved by describing appropriate research methods.

2. The principle of consistency. The principle of consistency implies that the educational material is studied in a certain sequence and in a logical sequence. This is a systematic view of the academic discipline. At the same time, the interrelationship of various theories and concepts are shown. For this, the topics of the curriculum should be structured and systematic. The studied material is divided into logical sections and topics. After that, the order and methodology of working with them will be established. Basic concepts and ideas are highlighted in each topic. Lesson materials are structured and connections are made between theories and facts. Some continuity and interdisciplinary should be maintained from one subject to another, from one course to another.

3. The principle of mental and emotional unity. According to this principle, teaching will be effective if students know the goals of education, the need to learn a given topic, and its personal or professional importance, and show a conscious interest in knowledge. At the same time, direct emotional interest in technical objects and phenomena is the strongest incentive to study electrical engineering. According to this principle, it is based on the belief that the teaching of science is necessary and useful only for the students themselves. On the other hand, it is wrong to choose only interesting topics that will involuntarily draw attention from the electrical supply course.

4. The principle of the unity of subject-oriented and individual education. Electricity supply in agriculture and water management as a science has its own characteristics compared to other sciences. On the one hand, it is a science that

has its own objective subject content, like other technical and humanitarian sciences. Therefore, it should be studied separately and objectively. On the other hand, the topic of this subject is personally relevant for each student. Therefore, it is necessary to apply the knowledge they have acquired to themselves and to apply it for self-affirmation. In this regard, adherence to the principle of integrity means maintaining the necessary balance of subject-oriented and person-oriented content in electrical sciences.

5. The principle of unity of theoretical and empirical knowledge. This principle is a clarification of the didactic principle of the unity of concrete and abstract things. In accordance with this principle, the teaching of the science of power supply combines, on the one hand, the description of theoretical ideas and their rationale. On the other hand, the specific empirical facts that underlie them should optimally integrate the concrete examples that they represent. Unfortunately, sometimes in textbooks of electrical supply, even in lectures, there are too many theoretical ideas that are not supported by concrete facts and examples. This principle requires to be established in the section “Science-education-production”. At the same time, this principle implies the analysis of events in reality based on personal views of the knowledge acquired from pedagogic sciences. This unites the work of the practical activities of the requirements in the application of knowledge to life and ensures the unity of theoretical knowledge and practical activities.

6. The principle of availability. The principle of accessibility requires that the content and methods of education depend on the individual characteristics of students, their interest in education, age characteristics and level of development. According to this principle, it is necessary to move from the simple to the complex, from the known to the unknown. The same content should be taught based on different knowledge and interests: a) students studying in the field of electricity supply; b) students studying in higher education in other technical specialties; c) students of secondary special educational institutions; d) students of general educational institutions.

7. The principle of demonstrability. The principle of demonstrability implies the unity of visual and verbal content, which is the most important psychological basis of understanding. Since visual images are important in teaching the science of electrical supply, in accordance with this principle, it is necessary to present information visually and use various visual aids. The principle of demonstrability is the most important in teaching the science of power supply.

Here it goes into the state of the principle of visualization. Visualization helps the learner better understand and remember the information presented. At the same time, it allows the brain to expand its ability to perceive a complex thing as a whole.

8. The principle of activity. The principle of activity is that the effective assimilation of knowledge should take place in active educational activities. In the implementation of this principle, the issues of forming the need for knowledge and developing the dialogic form of education are of great importance. At the same time, this principle is implemented by applying a problem-based approach to teaching, using practical methods of teaching (in the form of educational experiences, tests, psychological training, etc.).

9. The principle of connection with life and practice. The principle of connection with life and practice includes the connection of the teaching process of electrical supply science with practice, the wide use of real examples and facts on the subject of lessons. In addition, it serves to ensure that students can apply the knowledge they are learning in practice in various life situations.

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